

ADVERTISING SLOGAN AS A SPECIAL ISSUE OF ADVERTISING LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article discusses problems of advertising slogan which gives general definitions of "advertising" by scholars. In addition, it provides information about linguistic and specific features of advertising language.*

Keywords: *advertising, slogan, speech, language, advertising language, theory, methods.*

РЕКЛАМНЫЙ СЛОГАН КАК ОСОБЫЙ ВОПРОС РЕКЛАМНОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы рекламного слогана, даны общие определения учёных о «рекламе». Кроме того, он предоставляет информацию о лингвистических и специфических особенностях рекламного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *реклама, слоган, речь, язык, язык рекламы, теория, методы.*

INTRODUCTION

Advertising had developed since ancient times. The first forms of advertising messages were transferred by word of mouth, however, in the ruins of Pompeii commercial messages and election campaign displays had been found. Egyptians used Papyrus to create sales messages and wall posters, while in Greece and Rome lost-and-found advertising on papyrus was common. Wall or rock painting for commercial advertising is another manifestation of an ancient media. The expression "advertising" derives from the medieval Latin verb "advertere" and means "to direct one's attention". Goddard relates to this by saying that if an advertisement is to attract someone's attention in our "richly literate culture", copywriters are the ones responsible for finding a way. Advertising has a long history, Wright points that advertising started in ancient Babylon in about 3000 B.C when inscriptions for an ointment dealer, a scribe and a shoe maker were made on clay tablets. Sandage and Fryburager argue that Egyptians first wrote runaway-slave announcements on papyrus at about 3200 B.C. While in Greece and Rome lost-and-found advertising on papyrus was common. Wall or rock paintings for commercial advertising is another manifestation of an ancient media advertising form. The original meaning of advertisement was news and to advertise meant to take note or to consider. After the 15th century, it developed into to all the attention of another to something. In the 16th century, it was —to give notice of anything or to make generally known. It was not until the 18th century that the advertising became a pure commercial activity.

REVIEW

Advertising performs a variety of functions for any business with a product or service to sell. One of the most basic functions of advertising is to identify products and differentiate them from others. Another is called informational function. Advertising is used to communicate information about the product or service advertised, to inform, report, and describe the features and its location of sale. Directive function is typical of advertising. Language, pictures, or other devices are employed to influence the audience's action, emotions, beliefs and attitudes, and to persuade, advise, recommend and induce consumers to try new products and to suggest reuse. Advertising plays an increasing important role in today's world. Without it, the products or

services cannot flow from the distributors or sellers to the consumers or users. And buyers would not know about or remember products or services, and the modern industrial world would collapse.

The generally used abbreviation for advertisements is Ad. According to businessdictionary.com, advertising is something that is paid, it is supposed to be non-personal, it is public communication about goods, services, ideas, organizations, people, places, causes, through means of communication such as direct mail, telephone, print, radio, TV, and internet. Advertisements are public notices that inform and motivate perspective customers; they are an integral part of marketing. Their aim is to persuade customers to take the action that is intended by the advertiser. "Advertising, generally speaking, is the promotion of goods, services, companies and ideas, usually performed by an identified sponsor. Marketers see advertising as part of an overall promotional strategy." Advertisement is a concrete manifestation of advertising; "a paid public announcement appearing in the media." It goes without saying that advertising means promotion of goods, services and companies and that marketers see advertising as part of an overall promotional strategy. Another brief definition of advertising is given in Investor words glossary: "Description or presentation of a product, idea, or organization, in order to induce individuals to buy, support, or approve of it." Churchill and Peter define the advertising "as any announcement or persuasive message placed in the mass media in paid or donated time or space by an identified individual, company, or organization to serve a number of audience about products and persuade or remind them of buying, to convey information about the organization itself or issues important to the organization in order to create or enhance perception of the quality or reliability of a product, thus encouraging customer loyalty and repeat purchases". Leech states that "most advertising language comes under the broader heading of "loaded language" that is aimed to change the will, opinions or attitudes of its audience" Leech refers to the general style used in advertising as public colloquial because formal language is difficult, therefore advertiser favor a colloquial style to make contact with the general public regardless of their level of education. Finally, advertisement is a genre characterized by semiotic heterogeneity and is a culture-specific message incorporating various codes.

One of the most crucial components of advertisement language is the advertising slogan. Generally, slogan is understood as "a word or phrase that is easy to remember, used for example by a political party or in advertising to attract 23 people's attention or to suggest an idea quickly."

DISCUSSION

A slogan is a short phrase in part used to help form an image, identity, or position for a band or an organization and is established by repeating the phrase in a firm's advertisement and other public communication as well as through sales people, event promotions, and rocket launches. Similarly, Leech noted that slogan is short, laconic phrase that a company uses it over and over in its advertisement. It is especially useful to reinforce the product identity. A slogan can prove to be more powerful than a logo. People can remember and recite the advertisement slogan while they are unlikely to doodle over the logo. It is more important for the advertisement slogan to - clearly state what the advertisement is about than to be clever, but if the slogan can accomplish both, all the better. A slogan is defined by Cone as "a memorable phrase expressing an idea, purpose, or claim". In advertisements, the slogan generally accompanies the brand name

and/or logo. Slogans are important in an advertisement as they often become a primary association for the brand. According to Bovee and Arens, “the word slogan comes from 16th century Scottish Gaelic term for “battle cry”. And as a battle cry, slogans are usually short and simple, thus memorable and easy to repeat, distinguishing the product, service or company from its competitors. They add that there are many aspects of a language which allow copywriters get creative and chase the full potential of a slogan. Rhyming, alliteration or various figures of speech are just a few copy aids that can be very effective when writing an advertising slogan.

According to Bovee, advertising has never been as ubiquitous as it is nowadays. Language in advertising is typified by a slogan which is present in every advertisement. Slogans can be considered the heart of advertisements wherever they appear. Angela Goddard in her book “The language of advertising” titles these slogans the hooks which she calls “the initial piece of attention-seeking verbal language used to draw the reader in”. Slogans are the most important and condensed messages advertisers would like to send to their customers. Sharp and intelligent slogans can help advertisers leave unforgettable impressions on their potential customers’ minds. They provide continuity for a campaign and reduce a key theme or idea the company wants to be associated with its product or itself to a brief statement. According to Dean, cues in advertising are important to consumers in making inferences, reducing uncertainty and forming product preferences. Slogans are one of the possible intrinsic cues in advertising. In this context, the ad signature is much more than a name and its function transcends the mere identification of the advertiser. The signature has become an integral part of advertising’s rhetoric, contributing to the construction of the message as a whole. It is used as a closing element, which concludes the ad’s argumentation, and can be a graphic mark (commonly known as logo), campaign tagline (phrase, word or expression employed exclusively in an advertising campaign and expires with it) or slogan.

Adopting Vakratsas and Ambler (1999) model to study how advertising works, slogans are classified as an element of advertising input, since slogans convey a message as a whole. It is used as a closing element, which concludes the ad’s argumentation, and can be a graphic mark (commonly known as logo), campaign tagline (phrase, word or expression employed exclusively in an advertising campaign and expires with it) or slogan. Slogans contribute to the attainment of enhancing brand awareness and creating, supporting, or changing the brand perceptions and (re)positioning. This makes slogans one fundamental element in the (re)construction of brand identity, recognizing that slogans may have positive effects on brands. Slogans also provide continuity throughout advertising campaigns and facilitate the establishment and maintenance of a strong brand identity, enabling positive effects, namely: enhanced product differentiation, improved brand recall and improved brand evaluations.

Synthesizing, slogans are assumed to contribute positively to brand equity because they can help on: creating brand awareness by linking the brand to a product category; shaping brand evaluations by priming specific brand associations; shaping brand evaluations by transfer of likeability; reinforcing brand awareness and evaluations by serving as a memory aid. Concerning the creation of slogans, Stewart and Clark refer that a slogan must connect with the public in two areas - it must be understood by the consumer and be readily associated to the brand it represents. According to the perspectives of advertising decision-makers, Molian found that, on the first place, an effective slogan should be easy to remember, make a distinctive claim and be easily understood. On the second place, Molian’s findings indicate that the slogan should

highlight a customer benefit, convey a sense of mission and be credible. Kohli et al. (2007) provide theoretical guidelines for creating effective slogans. Although those guidelines were not empirically tested and proved, such authors recommend that a slogan should: - include the future's business; - position the brand in a clear way; - link the slogan to the brand; - be absolutely consistent from ad to ad and be repeated; - be used at the outset; - be creative. Advertising slogans and promotional tools enable companies to introduce themselves, their products, or services. In order for an advertising slogan to be effective in introducing a company or institution, it should be easily understood by consumers, and be associated with a specific brand. An advertising slogan along with brand name and logo are three key components of brand identity that establish companies' connections with the world around them.

Advertising slogans are often presented as jingles; because such slogans typically can adequately fulfill their duty which is improvement of remembering and recalling brand. According to Diez Arroyo (1998), the main purpose of slogans, which are brief and concise formulae, is to capture the consumer's attention and arouse his/her interest in the product. It is the syntax of concise, no-nonsense, to-the-point efficiency. Slogan differs from many other forms of writing because it is designed to be remembered and repeated word for word, to impress a brand and its message on the audience. Features of language of advertising and slogans. Leech's comprehensive study looks at following elements: Advertising situation, including participants, objects, medium of communication, and purpose or effect. Type of addressee: direct or indirect Products, media, audience, and aims and how the particulars of each influences the language used in advertising. Register, and how it is affected by discourse style, discourse mode, and discourse role.

Clauses, including imperative clauses, interrogative clauses, non-finite and minor clauses, and dependent clauses with "when", "if", and "because" Verbal groups, including simplicity, tense and aspect and "will" and "can". Nominal groups, including pre-modifiers such as genitives, comparatives and superlative adjectives and noun modifiers. Cohesion and lack of cohesion. Vocabulary, particularly adjectives and verbs Reference and vagueness of reference. Creative aspects, including orthographic oddities, grammatical breaches, lexical divergence, semantic infringements, contextual violation, figurative language, and ambiguity, including multiple meaning and homonymy. Stylistic devices, such as repetition, alliteration assonance, and rhyme. Leech developed the following principles of advertising slogans: Attention value, Readability, Memorability and Selling power. Attentive Value. The language of advertisement slogans must attract the attention of consumers in the most effective way (by means of stylistic contrast, elements of colloquial style, linguistic deviations, etc.). Memorability. The advertising slogan should produce a lasting impression on the people and make them remember the product either consciously or unconsciously (by the extensive use of simple words and phrases, as well as unusual word combinations and sentence structures).

Memorability is determined by readability which highlights the colloquial style and vocabulary so as to make the text easy to read and comprehend. Stylistically relevant phonetic devices (sound imitation, alliteration, rhythm and rhyme, etc.) tend to be effectively used for making the message easy to read and remember. Selling Power. The consumers buy products as a result of direct or indirect, conscious or unconscious influence. Altogether these effects determine the final aim of the advertising slogan – its ability to make a consumer buy the product, i.e. selling power. The selling power is mostly dependent on the uniqueness and

advantages of the product. The majority of the headlines finally turn out to be the slogans. The main function of the slogan is to keep continuity for a campaign. It is usually a brief, easily memorable statement that is connected with the product.

Bovee and Arens (1992) claim that slogan should stay the same for years, should be recognized immediately, customers should understand it. In his book “English in Advertising: A Linguistic Study of Advertising in Great Britain”, Leech (1972) maintains that the slogan is a short phrase used by the company in its advertisements to reinforce the identity of the brand. In his opinion, slogans are more powerful than companies’ logos and can be easily remembered and recited by people. Also, the scholar underlines that slogans have to clearly state the main idea of the advertisement, i.e. they have to be easy to understand. Godin refers to the advertising slogan as a “scenario”, which attracts a potential customer. The idea that the slogan is a tool that helps a customer to identify the brand is also maintained by Dowling and Kabanoff who state that advertising slogans are a few words that “appear beneath or beside the corporate name at the bottom of a print advertisement and are separated from the body copy for easy recognition”.

RESULTS

According to these authors, the advertising slogan is not only memorable itself, but also helps to memorize the brand or company. In Clow and Baack’s view, the advertising slogan is an easily remembered catchy phrase that makes a key point about the company’s image to the customer. In the article “The Importance of Ad Slogans”, Hamlin describes the advertising slogans as “catchy, declarative phrases that use devices such as metaphors, alliteration or rhymes with simple, vibrant language”, which, even without mentioning the company’s name or product, help people remember the brand. Advertising is crucial in our modern society and is one of those spheres where the use of language has to be employed in the most efficient and effective ways to transmit the message of the businesses to their customers. Therefore, advertising is very important and has become indispensable in our modern life. An advertising slogan can be treated as a memorable phrase (motto), catchy, deliberate and repetitive expression of an idea or purpose, used in various social contexts. The most frequent and important type of advertising is “commercial consumer advertising” which is advertising directed towards a mass audience with the aim of promoting sales of a commercial product or service. People pay more and more attention to the use of stylistic devices with an effort to make the advertisement sufficient, accurate and vivid and to provide rich imagination and plentiful associations for readers so as to stimulate their desire. The use of stylistic devices in advertisements aims at arousing and persuading consumers to buy what is advertised. And their proper use can make an advertisement sweet to the ear, and pleasing to both the eye and the mind.

CONCLUSION

Thus, stylistic devices are the best choice of language for the advertisers to make up ideal advertisements. Generally, the language of advertising is defined as a ‘loaded language’ (Leech). Its final aim is to change the will, opinions, or attitudes of people. In brief, advertising is one of the most effective tools of manipulation. The main principles of advertising slogans are as follows: Attention value, Readability, Memorability and Selling power. The principle of attentive value presupposes the fact that the advertising slogan should aim at attracting consumers’ attention in the most effective way by using a variety of stylistically charged linguistic resources. The principle of memorability is based on the idea that the advertising slogan is designed to make a lasting impression on the consumers and remember the product

either consciously or unconsciously. The principle of readability takes into account the extensive use of colloquial style and vocabulary to make the message easy to read and comprehend. The principle of selling power is based on the idea that the consumers have to buy products after being under direct or indirect, conscious or unconscious influence.

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